

Actions Speak Louder Than Words: Evidence-Based Trust Level Evaluation in Multi-Agent Systems

Nikolaos Fotos¹, Koffi Ismael Ouattara², Dimitrios S. Karas⁴, Ioannis Krontiris², Weizhi Meng³, and Thanassis Giannetsos⁴

¹ Department of Computer Architecture, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

`nikolaos.fotos@upc.edu`

² Huawei Technologies, Munich, Germany

`{koffi.ismael.ouattara,ioannis.krontiris}@huawei.com`

³ Lancaster University, Lancaster, United Kingdom

`w.meng3@lancaster.ac.uk`

⁴ Digital Security & Trusted Computing Group, Ubitech Ltd., Athens, Greece

`{dkaras,agiannetsos}@ubitech.eu`

Abstract. Trust assessment in multi-agent systems (MAS) is critical for ensuring reliable decision-making in dynamic, decentralized environments. However, existing methods for evaluating trust are domain-specific, fragmented, and difficult to generalize. To address this, we propose a generic methodology for trust level calculation that can be instantiated based on domain-specific requirements. We apply this methodology in a smart healthcare use case, where trust is assessed for medical data exchanged between smart ambulances and hospital backends. Through systematic experimentation, we evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of our approach, identifying key challenges that arise when applying such a trust assessment methodology in practice. These insights allow us to analyze fundamental gaps that must be addressed to further advance the formalization of trust assessment methodologies, bridging the gap between domain-specific trust models and a harmonized approach to trust computation.

Keywords: Trust · Trustworthiness · Trust Modeling · Subjective logic

1 Introduction

Multi-agent systems (MAS) are increasingly prevalent in fields such as autonomous mobility, smart grids, distributed artificial intelligence, and IoT networks. MAS rely on interactions between autonomous entities that must assess each other’s reliability to ensure safe and efficient performance. In this context, trust and trustworthiness are key constructs underpinning interactions among entities that often operate without a central authority. While trust is pivotal in decision-making in such environments, helping agents select collaborators, assess the

trustworthiness of incoming information, and mitigate threats from untrustworthy or hostile entities, it is usually confined to system integrity and dependability aspects excluding other important dimensions such as privacy, robustness, availability, and authenticity of the participating entities and their actions.

In such complex and dynamic systems, we often have to make trust decisions based on incomplete, conflicting, or uncertain information. Traditional probabilistic models assume that we have complete knowledge of all possibilities and their respective probabilities, but in dynamic, distributed environments, this is rarely the case. For example, a system might receive conflicting data from different data sources or communication channels. Also, not all data sources are equally reliable, and some may be compromised or faulty.

In such environments, the use of an evidence-based theory for trust assessment becomes essential, because it allows us to explicitly represent uncertainty. Rather than forcing a decision based on incomplete data, we can account for the fact that we do not have enough information, thus reflecting uncertainty in our trust assessments. Then, instead of discarding data that do not fully support or contradict a trust proposition, we can blend the evidence, representing both belief and disbelief while leaving room for uncertainty. This also allows us to dynamically adjust trust levels as more data become available.

A probabilistic framework that explicitly incorporates epistemic uncertainty and trust in information sources, making it useful in decision-making under uncertainty, is subjective logic. An opinion ω in subjective logic is a formal way of representing trust in a proposition by combining belief b (the degree to which the evidence supports the proposition), disbelief d (the degree to which the evidence contradicts the proposition) and uncertainty u (the degree to which the evidence is insufficient to make a clear judgment).

This triplet (b, d, u) is especially useful in environments where we often have incomplete or conflicting evidence, such as when data is missing, delayed, or of varying quality. In multi-agent systems, evidence is not always directly observable. Often, trustworthiness is assessed indirectly through a chain of agents that pass along their own trust assessments or evidence. That means agents might have to rely on *referrals* from other trusted agents to form their opinions. Each agent provides an opinion, which is then *discounted* based on the trustworthiness of the referring agent. This allows for the propagation of trust assessments through a network of agents.

In addition, in environments where evidence is uncertain or incomplete, combining the opinions of multiple agents helps improve the overall trust perception by gathering multiple perspectives. If multiple agents provide trust opinions on the same proposition (for example, whether a data source is accurate), the trust evaluation of an agent can use *fusion* operators to combine these opinions into a single consolidated trust score.

However, the dynamic nature of MAS requires that trust assessment is not only based on reasoning under uncertainty, but it also ensures that the evidence used to compute trust opinions is verifiable. Trust cannot be randomly assigned or assumed from previous interactions, but rather must be continuously verified

and updated through collectable evidence. This principle aligns with Zero Trust security, which dictates that no entity should be inherently trusted without validation. Verification of evidence is related to the use of *Trust Anchors*, since they are the starting point for verifying the chain of trust.

Calculating trust opinions has typically been evaluated so far within a specific trust relationship and context, making it challenging to develop a generalized trust assessment methodology that can be applied across different domains. This is further aggravated by the fact that such different domains may have multifaceted constraints and objectives. Consider, for instance, the case of Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM) services, in the automotive domain, where it is critical to assess trustworthiness in terms of integrity, without compromising the safety-critical profile of the running services (e.g., Collision Avoidance). However, in the context of less critical operations such as Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums (GLAM), the focus is primarily shifted to the integrity of a media asset while ensuring data governance in a privacy-preserving manner [10]. These concepts, while interrelated, require clearer terminological distinctions to facilitate effective trust assessment and management within decentralized environments of mixed-criticality.

Existing approaches often define trustworthiness in isolated scenarios, limiting their applicability when trust sources and trust relationships change. Without a structured and harmonized approach to trust assessment, interoperability between trust models remains difficult, and trust evaluations are often ad hoc, domain-dependent, and incompatible across systems. This requires shifts-of-paradigms, where instead of traditional trust assessment methodologies, focusing on the establishment of peer-to-peer communication relationships, we need to adopt generic trust assessment sequences with an increased degree of adaptability to cope with all aforementioned challenges.

1.1 Problem Statement and Contributions

To this end, a Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) is needed to provide a process for evaluating trust in a systematic way, which is not specific to a domain and remains flexible enough to accommodate different trust models and trust sources. Such a framework would enable the modelling of trust relationships, the management of trust sources, the collection of evidence from these sources, and the evaluation of trust expressions based on the evidence. The outcome of this process is a computed Actual Trust Level (ATL) that quantifies the trustworthiness of an entity or data source in a given context.

Recently, there has been considerable effort to define the architecture of such a framework, but again this has been done in the context of specific (mixed-criticality) domains such as the safety-critical V2X [27] and the privacy-focused image processing [3] realm. However, the considered trust networks to be built make several assumptions about the trust model and trust expression representation. The key challenge, therefore, lies in understanding the abstraction of trust assessment, defining its fundamental components, and identifying the core challenges in developing a generic trust assessment framework for multi-agent

systems. We argue that establishing a structured approach to trust expression generation, evidence collection, and ATL computation is a crucial step towards achieving this goal.

In this paper we make the following contributions:

1. We propose a structured abstraction for trust level calculation, defining a *general process for computing the Actual Trust Level (ATL)* of some data, or entity. Our methodology abstracts the key steps of ATL computation (i.e., expression generation, evidence collection, and trust evaluation) allowing for different instantiations depending on domain-specific needs. This abstraction establishes a foundation for a generic trust assessment methodology, ensuring that trust evaluation can handle evolving trust models, incorporate different sources of uncertainty, and support dynamic multi-agent environments.
2. We instantiate the above abstraction and apply it to calculate the ATL of medical data sent in a specific use case from the healthcare domain, where smart ambulances interact with hospital backends. Thus, we validate our ATL methodology and, most importantly, we are able to evaluate it using systematic experiments. The experiences gained from these experiments allow us to extract fundamental insights into the challenges that arise from applying such a methodology in practice.
3. Having identified these challenges out of the experimental evaluation, we then perform a more in-depth analysis of the *fundamental gaps* that must be addressed to develop a *generic trust assessment framework* for multi-agent systems, one that is not constrained by domain-specific assumptions. Through this systematic examination, we formulate concrete research problems that remain open, providing a structured foundation for advancing trust assessment methodologies.

1.2 Related Work

Trust modelling has been studied extensively in a variety of areas, including cybersecurity, autonomous systems, and distributed AI. Traditional trust assessment techniques can be broadly categorized into probabilistic models, rule-based systems, and reputation-based systems. Reputation-based models aggregate historical interactions to assess an agent’s trustworthiness. Huynh et al.[14] introduced an integrated trust and reputation model, while Sabater and Sierra[25] reviewed computational models, highlighting challenges like collusion and the assumption that past behaviour predicts future trustworthiness, which may not hold in dynamic MAS environments.

Probabilistic models, such as Bayesian inference [28] and Dempster-Shafer theory [29], provide formal reasoning under uncertainty. Bayesian inference enables adaptive trust updating, but relies on predefined structures and struggles with conflicting observations. Dempster-Shafer theory introduces degrees of belief and plausibility, but complicates the interpretation of uncertainty. Subjective logic offers a more flexible approach by incorporating belief, disbelief, and uncertainty. Jøsang [17] applied subjective logic to trust networks, facilitating the

combination of multiple trust opinions. Cerutti et al. [5] empirically validated subjective logic operators, demonstrating their effectiveness in handling conflicting information and uncertainty. Trust models integration into multi-agent decision-making has been studied for improved coordination and cooperation. [4] examined trust decision mechanisms with a focus on the subjective logic for evaluating potential interactions. [26] examined context-based trust decisions and models that reason with context data to update trust judgments.

While there have been efforts in the literature for the design of generic multi-agent trust assessment frameworks, existing solutions make certain assumptions that limit their potential for universal applicability. For instance, the capability for the adoption of zero-trust principles is limited, as existing approaches consider agents which are assumed to provide trustworthy information and obey control actions dictated by a central or distributed coordinator [7], or are based on design-time trust opinions that do not consider the notion of bootstrapping trust [13]. The definition of uncertainty in existing works is also limited in scope, as it is typically approached as the lack of evidence to support a specific probability [20] [6] and does not consider uncertainty associated with the quantification process or with confidence in each type of evidence.

Several studies have explored different approaches to trust modelling and evaluation, but with inherent challenges on how to cope with dynamic (continuously changing) environments where a variety of evidence should be used for quantifying trustworthiness. Hermann et al. [13] examined how evidence can be transformed into opinion, but their work was limited to a simple trust model that relied on a single type of evidence. Petrovska et al. [24] proposed a method for constructing and evaluating expressions within a subjective trust network; however, their approach cannot support composite propositions due to inherent design constraints. Kargl et al. [21] introduced a framework combining ATL and RTL within a CIM use case, but relied on a simplistic trust model without a generalized methodology. Similarly, EU Project CONNECT [27] introduced the Trust Assessment Framework, but faced limitations in handling composite propositions due to its reliance on subjective trust networks. Cheng et al. [6] presented a comprehensive framework for quantifying trustworthiness within MAS, using subjective logic to formalize trust relationships. However, their approach assumes the presence of a trusted observer, and the evidence for trust assessments is derived solely from agent behaviour.

2 Trust Assessment Preliminaries

One of the intrinsic characteristics of a trust assessment framework is that it is context-dependent. The results of a trust assessment task are always tailored to a specific trust property characterizing a specific object. **Trust properties** refer to specific properties of the system that need to be assessed for their trustworthiness and they may refer to an agent or a data item [1]. The evaluation of a trust property in a specific target object forms a **trust proposition**. The evaluation of a trust proposition from the perspective of a source trust object is captured

through a **trust relationship**. Secondly, in the context of distributed, multi-agent systems, trust relationships may capture the interdependencies between multiple trust objects (agents) that capture transitive or referral trust.

So far, we have used “trustworthiness” and “trust” interchangeably. Trustworthiness refers to the likelihood of a trustee fulfilling the trustor’s expectations in a given context, focusing on the trustee’s actual behaviour. In contrast, trust is assessed from the trustor’s perspective. Following the definition in [9], we define trust as the willingness of the trustor to take risk based on a subjective belief (i.e., trustworthiness) that a trustee will exhibit reliable behaviour to maximize the trustor’s interest under uncertainty in a given context.

The main challenge in quantifying trustworthiness according to evidence-based theory [30] lies in establishing *trust sources* to extract evidence and mapping it to trust relationships. In distributed multi-agent systems, different entities may hold varying opinions on a trust proposition, requiring uncertainty modelling to account for conflicting or missing evidence. Subjective Logic [15] is a mathematical theory that enable us to probabilistically represent belief based on operational evidence while incorporating uncertainty to handle contradicting or absent information. Through this approach, evidence reported by trust sources forms concrete trust opinions over trust relationships, where, in its simplest form, a trust opinion corresponds to a binary trust property (e.g., whether a trust object maintains integrity). In this case, the trust opinion of the binary trust property x is a binomial opinion $\omega_x = (b_x, d_x, u_x, a_x)$, where:

- b_x : Belief mass supporting that x stands,
- d_x : Disbelief mass supporting that x does not stand,
- u_x : Uncertainty mass representing the vacuity of evidence in favour of a specific outcome (belief or disbelief),
- a_x : Base rate (initial probability) supporting that x stands, assuming prior knowledge over the proposition,
- $b_x + d_x + u_x = 1$.

The trust opinion that expresses an assessment of a trust proposition from the perspective of a particular source is called the **actual trust level (ATL)** of the proposition. Trust decisions based on ATL values can be formulated in various ways, including defining an acceptable range for the belief mass probability, setting an uncertainty threshold, or computing a scalar value incorporating the projected probability of a trust opinion. The **required trust level (RTL)** refers to a formally defined criterion or threshold that determines which ATL values are deemed acceptable for taking a trust decision within a given context.

3 ATL Methodology and Trust Assessment Framework

Identifying a generic methodology for calculating the ATL value for a trust proposition is crucial, especially in multi-agent, distributed environments. Having such a methodology ensures that trust can be evaluated and propagated consistently across various agents, each with different perspectives, evidence sources,

and operational constraints. Broadly speaking, obtaining an ATL value for a trust proposition involves the following steps: *Expression Generation*, *Evidence Collection*, and *Expression Evaluation*. We have to highlight that in what follows, we focus on a model where the TAF has access to evidence coming from all relevant trust objects. This need to be weakened in federated models, as we will discuss in Section 5 (C5).

3.1 Expression Generation

This step involves the construction of a concrete expression for the calculation of the ATL value for a trust proposition that is evaluated by a **trustor** - i.e., the trust object that acts as the one that conducts the trust assessment. This expression should take into account all the involved trust relationships that are relevant to the trustor to reflect its belief over the trust proposition. These expressions can vary in complexity, ranging from simple atomic expressions to more complex logical combinations of multiple propositions.

In its simplest form, an expression refers to an *atomic trust proposition* that can be derived from a single evidence claim. For instance, assuming the availability of a trust source that provides evidence about the secure boot of a device, an atomic trust proposition can be formed as the "medical sensor A has booted up its firmware correctly". Of course, realistic propositions may require the combination of multiple atomic trust propositions to derive a decision about the trustworthiness of a trust object. For example, in the smart ambulance example, the trustworthiness of an over-the-air firmware update in the vehicle's internal topology can be treated as a *composite proposition* that involves the assessment of atomic trust propositions, namely the fact that the medical sensors and gateways have booted up their firmware correctly *AND* the configuration integrity of the related devices stands upon completion of the update process.

Regardless of whether the trust proposition is atomic or composite, there is a clear need to define concrete operations among the different trust relationships that represent the topology under evaluation. The existence of concrete subjective logic operators allows actions such as the calculation of trust opinions that refer to transitive trust relationships (Discounting operator [18], [23]), and how to derive a trust opinion on a **trustee**, that is, the trust object (node or data) that is associated with a target trust proposition, acting as sink node of multiple trust relationships (Fusion operator [16]). These two operators are important for aggregating trust opinions for any atomic trust proposition. Additional subjective logic operators [15] (e.g., Multiplication, AND, OR), allow the calculation of composite trust propositions.

Trust Model The trust model representation serves as a structural framework that defines the relationships between different trust objects and the trust propositions we want to evaluate. These models allow us to clearly represent how trust is built, which entities are involved, and what aspects of trust need to be assessed. From this model, we can derive *trust expressions* that represent how trustworthiness is calculated based on evidence and trust relationships. There

are various ways to represent trust relationships and their trustworthiness ([17], [11], [22], [12]). In this work, we employ the Subjective Logic Trust Network [17], as it allows us to express all the trust relationships between all entities in the form of a graph. In addition, it enables the concrete modelling of uncertainty across all trust relationships as their corresponding trustworthiness is expressed as a subjective logic opinion $\omega = (b_x, d_x, u_x, a_x)$. Consequently, the definition of a trust model requires the following: (i) a concrete representation of the system trust relationships G , (ii) a set of trust sources $\tau\sigma$ to collect evidence for each trust relationship, (iii) a function f (e.g., Equation 1) that maps trustworthiness evidence to trust opinions, and (iv) a trustor agent α on behalf of whom the queries should be made.

3.2 Evidence Collection and Opinion Formation

Depending on the trust proposition being assessed, different types of evidence may be required. In the context of security-related trust properties, trust sources include detection mechanisms, e.g., Intrusion Detection Systems, Misbehaviour Detection Systems, or mechanisms to evaluate the existence and/or enforcement of security claims such as secure boot, configuration integrity etc. In principle, the received evidence can be distinguished into two main categories depending on the inferred claims. On the one hand, there is binary evidence that allows the verifier to compute whether the claim exists or not. For instance, this is the case of the secure boot certificate chain that allows a verifier to make an informed decision that the prover has executed its secure boot process. On the other side, there is evidence that results in claims expressed in the form of a range. This is the case of some Misbehaviour Detection systems that provide a score - e.g., confidence level - about abnormal behaviour of a trustee. This diversity of the evidence outcome introduces the need for robust quantification mechanisms to enable the quantification of trustworthiness in a trust model while using heterogeneous evidence and trust sources.

Once evidence has been collected, the next step is to form opinions about each trust proposition. According to [8], [19], the subjective belief that a trust proposition x stands - in a more formal way this is equivalent to the belief that the value of a random variable X is x - can be quantified in relation to the positive evidence that support it. Similarly, the disbelief can be quantified in relation to the positive evidence:

$$b_x = \frac{r_x}{W + r_x + s_x}, d_x = \frac{s_x}{W + r_x + s_x}, u_x = \frac{W}{W + r_x + s_x}, \quad (1)$$

where r_x corresponds to the number of evidence supporting the trust proposition, s_x any other evidence against it, and W is the non-informative prior weight in the absence of positive evidence r_x or negative evidence s_x . An additional approach is to define an activation function in order to describe how much belief or disbelief should be increased when a specific evidence for a protection mechanism is in place (or decreased when it is not). Of course, this activation

function may vary between the types of evidence and their importance to the realization of the trust opinion. This function could be linear, exponential, etc.

3.3 Expression Evaluation

Expression evaluation is the process of integrating the trust opinions derived during the evidence collection phase by applying logical operators and subjective logic mechanisms to combine and propagate trust. Logical operators such as AND, OR, and NOT define how trustworthiness is evaluated across multiple propositions, while trust-specific operators like discounting and fusion handle scenarios involving referrals and multiple independent or dependent sources of evidence. The resulting trust opinion, expressed as a triplet of belief (b), disbelief (d), and uncertainty (u), provides a formalized representation of the overall trustworthiness of the evaluated expression.

Definition 1 (Logical Operators). *Let A be an agent, and let X and Y be two random variables. Suppose that the analyst A holds an opinion $\omega_{X=x}^A$ on the event $X = x$ and $\omega_{Y=y}^A$ on the event $Y = y$. The opinion of analyst A on the compound statements $(X = x) \wedge (Y = y)$ and $(X = x) \vee (Y = y)$ can be computed using the following logical operators:*

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_{(X=x) \wedge (Y=y)}^A &= \omega_{X=x}^A \cdot \omega_{Y=y}^A, \\ \omega_{(X=x) \vee (Y=y)}^A &= \omega_{X=x}^A \sqcup \omega_{Y=y}^A.\end{aligned}$$

Moreover, for the negation operator, the opinion is simply inverted. Logical operators is on the algebra of variables.

Definition 2 (Trust discounting). *Let A be an agent seeking to form an opinion about a variable X or a specify event $X = x$. A has a referral trust ω_B^A on another agent B , which holds an opinion on X or $X = x$. The trust-discounted opinion of A , derived from B 's opinion, is computed as follows:*

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_{X=x}^{[A;B]} &= \omega_B^A \otimes \omega_{X=x}^B \\ \omega_X^{[A;B]} &= \omega_B^A \otimes \omega_X^B\end{aligned}$$

It is important to note that referral trust is context-dependent and applies to a specific domain. In this case, A referral trust on B is about providing good advice regarding X .

Definition 3 (Fusion). *Let A be an agent seeking to form an opinion about a variable X . Assume that A has two independent sources or methods for deriving this opinion, denoted as P and Q . The fused opinion, which combines the perspectives from P and Q , is defined as:*

$$\omega_X^A = \omega_X^{P \& Q} = \omega_X^P \odot \omega_X^Q \quad (2)$$

Fusion operators is on the algebra of agents. The choice of the fusion operator depends on the nature of the opinions being combined.

Example: Suppose we form an opinion based on images from two cameras and wish to fuse them. If the cameras share common angles, their opinions are correlated, suggesting that an averaging or weighted fusion method may be appropriate. Conversely, if the cameras capture entirely different angles, their opinions are independent, making cumulative fusion a more suitable approach.

The evaluation process dynamically accounts for factors such as uncertainty and conflicting evidence. For instance, when two trust sources provide inconsistent opinions about a proposition of the same variable, the evaluation might incorporate this conflict by increasing uncertainty in the resulting trust opinion depending on the fusion operator. Specialized operators such as discounting adjust trust based on the reliability of intermediary agents, while fusion combines multiple opinions, sometimes with weighted confidence levels to ensure fairness and accuracy. This adaptability is especially crucial in dynamic environments, where real-time updates to evidence and contextual changes require continuous re-evaluation of trust expressions. By ensuring consistency, robustness, and adaptability, the expression evaluation phase supports accurate trust assessments in complex, multi-agent systems.

4 ATL Methodology in Practice

To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed ATL methodology, we apply it to the practical use case of a smart ambulance equipped with Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) for patient health monitoring and healthcare during transit. Core challenges evaluated include (i) the ability of the envisioned trust expression (e.g., through a trust model) to cope with dynamic environments where ambulances can enrol and detach from the hospital domain, and (ii) the evaluation of the trust assessment process under different trust requirements depending on the hospital organization.

Figure 1 depicts the trust assessment flow in parallel with the use case topology, which consists of CMD sensors (S_1, S_2, S_n), connected to gateway devices (G) that relay the patient data (e.g., Respiratory and Blood pressure) to the associated healthcare organization backend. The backend triggers the initialization of the TAF, which in turn collects the trust relationships (referral and functional) of the topology and instantiates the trust model based on the trust requirements (e.g., RTL) of the organization. This enables the collection of the trustworthiness evidence relevant to the ATL expression for the target trust proposition. Collection of fresh evidence triggers the re-evaluation of the ATL expression, followed by the reporting of the trust decision to the backend.

Note that, while we assume that the TAF has access to fresh and observable evidence from the available trust sources, this is not always the case in multi-agent cross-domain use cases. However, as demonstrated in Section 5, such limitations can be lifted through the federation of the TAF.

Fig. 1: Architecture of the running example showing the operational data flow and the trust relationships within a smart ambulance topology.

Entity	Description
TAF	The agent that performs the trust assessment framework considering the trust requirements of a healthcare organization.
ECG_i	The trust proposition under evaluation which is stated as " <i>The ECG Data coming from the medical service graph chain of smart ambulance i is communicated with integrity assurance</i> ".
ω_{ECG}^{TAF}	Trust opinion assessed by the TAF on the trustworthiness of a piece of ECG or GNSS data with respect to integrity, during transit (equivalent to communication integrity assurances)
$\omega_{Amb_i}^{TAF}$	Trust opinion assessed by the TAF on the trustworthiness of the smart ambulance high end device, Amb_i , to capture and transmit ECG (or GNSS) data, whose integrity has not been compromised.
$\omega_{ECG}^{Amb_i}$	Trust opinion evaluated by the TAF on the trustworthiness of the smart ambulance, Amb_i , over its own data with respect to the integrity of it not being compromised. For the purposes of this evaluation, this trust opinion is constantly set to (1,0,0). This signals that the smart ambulance Amb_i has full belief over the trustworthiness of its data integrity.

Table 1: Glossary for trust model of the running example

4.1 Instantiating the ATL methodology in the Running Example

To conduct the trust assessment task within the framework of the running example, we follow the methodology outlined in Section 3. The first step is to identify the trust propositions to be evaluated and specify the expression for producing the corresponding ATL. This use case focuses on evaluating the trustworthiness of Electrocardiography (ECG) data transmitted with integrity assurances. The trust model representing the trust relationships and propositions for a single ambulance in a healthcare organization network is depicted in Figure 2, but it is possible to update the model with additional trust relationships if additional ambulances join the network. The terminology used for the trust model definition is summarized in Table 1.

Based on the trust model definition and the available subjective logic operations, the ATL value for the defined atomic trust proposition related to Amb_i can be calculated following the evaluation of the subsequent equation:

$$\omega_{ECG_i}^{TAF} \oplus (\omega_{Amb_i}^{TAF} \otimes \omega_{ECG_i}^{Amb_i}) \quad (3)$$

According to the ATL Methodology, the second step refers to the *Evidence Collection and Opinion Formation*. The set of evidence claims that are available in the running example is summarized in Table 2. For the trust opinion on the integrity of the smart ambulance topology, attestation evidence is collected proving the correct configuration of the topology (i.e., running the correct software stack). For the trust opinion on the integrity of the data directly from the trustor agent the available data traces are used. The extracted evidence claims from the data traces show indications that the patient data are transmitted successfully without any cyclic redundancy check (CRC) errors. In addition, the data traces include evidence pertaining to the resilience of the communication channel. To provide more evidence on the runtime execution of the smart ambulance gateway device, traces regarding the isolation of the device applications are provided. Finally, a data trace includes a network telemetry metric, namely the round-trip time corresponding to the transmission of the data. Based on the availability of evidence, we use Equation 1 to quantify the incoming evidence in trust - subjective logic - opinions.

Fig. 2: Trust model capturing the trust relationships of a smart ambulance i

The final step is to invoke the *Expression Evaluation* phase that yields the ATL value. To this end, we adopt the domain-agnostic TAF of [27] and apply the trust model of the smart ambulance use case depicted in Figure 2, the trust sources probing the ambulance topology, and the quantification function of Equation 1. We define two distinct epochs for evaluating the trust assessment task in healthcare organizations with different trust requirements: (i) Organization A, which models uncertainty by setting $W = 2$ (see Equation 1) and an RTL belief threshold of 0.85. (ii) Organization B, which allows for more uncertainty in opinion formation with $W = 4$ and an RTL belief threshold of 0.75.

Organization A (RTL belief threshold: 0.85, $W = 2$)			
Opinion	Default $\omega(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{u})$	Evidence	Trust Property
$\omega_{Amb_i}^{TAF}$	(0, 0, 1)	Binary Integrity Measurement List	Software Stack Configuration Integrity
$\omega_{ECG_i}^{TAF}$	(0, 0, 1)	CRC Checks/Sequence numbers	Communication Integrity
		Netflow headers	Communication Resilience
		Isolation level	Source Integrity
		Round-Trip time	Communication Availability

Table 2: Trust model information for organization A: Trustworthiness evidence and trust quantification weights.

(a) ATL belief fluctuation during Epoch 1 (Uncertainty weight $W=2$) (b) ATL belief fluctuation during Epoch 2 (Uncertainty weight $W=4$)

Fig. 3: ATL belief fluctuations for the three smart ambulance nodes

4.2 Evaluation

For evaluating the trust assessment process, we first set up three smart ambulance vehicles, as well as two healthcare organizations representing the two epochs, each one of which is running a trust assessment application in their backend. Then, for each epoch, the smart ambulances transmit ECG data to the backend of the corresponding organization. At the same time, a trace message is reported by the ambulance to the trust assessment application for quantifying the trust opinions on the trust model. Upon reception of new traces, the trust assessment application recalculates the ATL for the target trust proposition. For both epochs, the traces report discrepancies in the network quality of the patient data transmission. In contrast to the rest of the evidence claims that have a binary outcome, the level of network degradation depends on the latency of the message delivery. Thus, considering Equation 1, a weighted scheme for trust quantification is needed. In our work, this is implemented by an implicit weighting mechanism where the lowest network degradation level counts as multiple evidence in favour of the disbelief factor of the trust opinion $\omega_{ECG_i}^{TAF}$.

Figure 3 presents the fluctuations in the belief factor of the ATL trust opinion when fresh evidence arrives at the trust assessment application for both epochs. Epoch 1 is demonstrated in Figure 3a, where it is shown that the belief factor has four levels, representing the network degradation levels defined in the trust quantification functions. When all evidence claims are positive, the maximum ATL belief value is set close to the 0.9 threshold. This is due to the modelling of uncertainty with weight $W = 2$ (as per Equation 1), thus not allowing dogmatic ATL values (i.e., trust opinions with uncertainty set to 0). The trust requirements of Organization A specify a minimum belief threshold of 0.7, allowing for a positive trust decision even if network quality experiences a slight decline. Finally, if a smart ambulance node is inactive for a period of time, it is unregistered from the trust model structure, leading to a belief value of 0 (e.g., Vehicle 2 in the second half of Epoch 1 in Figure 3a).

Conversely, Figure 3b presents how the hardening of trust requirements impacts the ATL belief in Epoch 2. Modelling uncertainty limits the maximum ATL belief that can be attained with the available evidence (Challenge 2). Thus, increasing the uncertainty weight to $W = 4$ results in an ATL below the 0.8 threshold, even when all claims are positive. Secondly, the strict RTL belief threshold does not allow any network quality drop. This is intrinsically linked to both the specification of a trust quantification function (Challenge 1) for properly depicting the ATL of the evaluated propositions and the accurate derivations of the RTL constraints (Challenge 3) leading to an informed trust decision.

In addition to the evaluation of the runtime TAF, we also use the running example for the evaluation of the proper specification of the trust propositions. Specifically, ECG_i is specified as an atomic trust proposition that can be quantified based on the ATL expression of Equation 3 and the evidence of Table 1, some of which pertains to the quality of the data transmission channel. While this is used for materializing a trust proposition related to integrity assurances, it can be argued that it is more suitable as an indication of availability of patient data. This raises the need to evaluate the extent to which the definition of trust propositions affects the ATL trust opinion and, ultimately, the trust decision.

In this section, we evaluate how the definition of the trust proposition affects the ATL trust opinion, considering healthcare organization A with $W = 2$. To this end, Table 3 presents the ATL results when the integrity and availability trust properties are treated as either atomic or composite trust propositions, for the cases where all evidence claims are positive (first column) and when there is negative evidence on exactly one evidence claim (second column).

The first row of Table 3 represents the baseline execution of the running example, considering all available evidence claims. However, considering a trust opinion for the ATL constructed solely on the network quality (i.e., round-trip time) evidence claim, as shown in the second row, demonstrates that using only a single evidence claim leads to ATL trust opinions with high uncertainty. In addition, the evaluation of the ATL without the network quality evidence claim in the third row shows that the reduction in the number of evidence claims leads to lower belief and higher uncertainty compared to the baseline execution where all evidence is considered.

Breaking the proposition into atomic trust propositions (by separating the evidence claims in the relevant trust propositions) allows for the definition of composite propositions using subjective logic (SL) operators. However, while it is possible to create composite propositions for realistic trust assessment queries, it is important to consider that all atomic trust propositions comprising the composite one need to be associated with sufficient evidence. For instance, the fourth row of the table demonstrates a composite proposition considering both integrity and availability, and the use of the SL Multiplication operator enables the quantification of independent trust opinions for both integrity and availability. These results demonstrate that the lack of sufficient evidence for the availability atomic trust proposition leads to an ATL with high uncertainty (0.52). In addition, it is shown that negative evidence leads to a decrease in the sensitivity of the ATL,

since it decreases to 0.39 when one of the three available claims reports negative evidence on the integrity property, while it decreases to 0.19 when the only available claim reports negative evidence on availability.

It is worth noting that the negative evidence related to the integrity proposition refers to the isolation level as recorded in the data trace message, and forms the opinion $\omega_{ECG_i}^{TAF}$. We did not consider the case of negative evidence in the $\omega_{Amb_i}^{TAF}$ opinion, as the reception of negative evidence on the software stack integrity of the smart ambulance gateway device would render the traces as invalid and not processable by the trust assessment application. Finally, the lack of high ATL belief values is further supported by the complete decomposition of the integrity trust proposition into atomic trust propositions, each of which is constructed by a single type of the available evidence claims. Specifically, according to Table 2, having multiple atomic trust propositions, each based on a single piece of evidence, results in ATL trust opinions with high vagueness and uncertainty. Consequently, as discussed in Challenge 1 (see Section 5), a key aspect in conducting accurate trust assessments is determining the appropriate level of atomicity of the trust propositions.

Proposition	ATL_+	ATL_-	Comment
Integrity as an atomic prop.	(0.86, 0, 0.14)	(0.72, 0.14, 0.14)	All evidence claims from the data traces are quantified as a single trust opinion $\omega_{ECG_i}^{TAF}$.
Availability as an atomic prop	(0.33, 0, 0.67)	(0, 0.33, 0.67)	A separate trust opinion for the ATL, that is constructed based on the network quality evidence.
Integrity as an atomic prop.	(0.83, 0, 0.17)	(0.66, 0.17, 0.17)	Network degradation evidence claim is excluded from the opinion quantification.
Integrity AND Availability	(0.48, 0, 0.52)	Integrity fails: (0.39, 0.17, 0.44) Availability fails: (0.19, 0.33, 0.48)	Integrity and Availability are expressed as atomic trust propositions. The use of the Multiplication SL operator is employed to calculate the composite proposition.
Integrity as a composite prop.	(0.21, 0, 0.79)	(0.05, 0.33, 0.62)	Each evidence claim is mapped to an atomic trust opinion and the Multiplication SL operator is used to derive the Integrity of the patient data as a composite proposition.

Table 3: ATL evaluations (ATL_+ with positive and ATL_- with a single negative evidence claim) related to the patient data from a smart ambulance topology when modelling properties differently: atomic vs. composite propositions.

5 Desiderata for a Generic Trust Assessment Sequence

From the above analysis, it becomes obvious that while building trusted and trustworthy (decentralized) systems is essential, it is a complex, multifaceted problem. Trust and trustworthiness concepts (Section 2), while interrelated, require clearer terminological distinctions to facilitate effective trust assessment and management. This is particularly important in the quest to derive a generic ATL methodology, employing a universal sequence for trust, agnostic to the target domain and capable of coping with the different trust requirements and topology complexities: an assessment of trust beliefs, a trust decision with possibly (but not necessarily) a risk-taking action, and finally feedback on the outcome

of the trusting action back to the input factors for the trust beliefs. Depending on the context within which the trust encounter takes place, different elements within the steps of the sequence can have more weight or are more relevant, but the sequence itself should be universal. However, another question that comes forth is how to enrich this sequence with the **perspective of distrust or uncertainty**. From our evaluation (Section 4.2), it becomes apparent that trust and uncertainty are not simply two ends of the same continuum. *How uncertainty is quantified and captured as part of a trust expression has a great impact on the trust decision-making process*: Higher uncertainty weight reduces the maximum attainable belief in ATL computations.

Therefore, it is imperative to overcome all these gaps in our knowledge on the relationship between trust and distrust processes so as to be able to build and maintain trust networks that shall operate correctly amid uncertainty in measurements and observations. The conceptual exercise that we undertook in this paper, considering the complex healthcare environment, aims to manifest such an attempt towards **trust assessment generalization**.

In what follows, we critically reflect on the identified core pillars that heavily affect the trust-aware decision making process and highlight outstanding issues that need to be further researched. In particular: (i) How does the presence of positive vs. negative evidence affect the calculation of ATL belief values? Depending on the substantive content of the input evidence, negative evidence seem to significantly lower belief values, affecting the perception of the trustor; (ii) How to best balance the expressiveness of the trust propositions against ATL accuracy and sensitivity? The structure of the trust propositions (atomic vs. composite) is a crucial element that influences the attainable (dis-) trust belief calculations; (iii) How to maintain an up-to-date view of the overall trust assessment of a topology? Since the trust relationships contain heterogeneous nodes, the trustworthiness should be assessed based on different and varying trust sources. Additionally, the available trust sources might change over time which, in turn, necessitates a dynamic trust re-valuation; (iv) Finally, what are the interoperability challenges and how they affect multi-agent trust assessments. Variations in trust requirements across organizations necessitate a harmonized evaluation approach. These findings also provide sufficient evidence on the feasibility of the proposed trust assessment methodology as a viable candidate.

C1 - Specifying the ATL Expression: The starting point of the ATL methodology is to identify the optimal set of accumulators and aggregate all relevant trust opinions related to a target proposition. At the same time, in a dynamic environment such as the one examined in the running example, it is essential to update the overall ATL expression when a new behaviour is observed in the system (e.g., a CMD sensor is securely on-boarded in the smart ambulance topology). Thus, the first question to be answered when instantiating the ATL methodology, is *how to model trust relationships of a target system in a systematic way so as to construct the equations for the ATL?*

In this work, we have adopted the trust model representation but, as demonstrated in Chapter 2, there are various strategies towards this. Regardless of the

strategy employed, it is clear that identifying the target trust proposition heavily affects the number and type of evidence to be collected which, when osculated, results in the trust expression and the calculation of the ATL. In fact, as demonstrated in the evaluation, the accuracy of the ATL is directly dependent on the level of atomicity of trust propositions. In an ideal atomic trust proposition, quantification should not require evidence aggregation, as each trust opinion is based on a single evidence type. An approach to achieve this low-level breakdown would be to define one atomic trust proposition per attack vector mapped to the enforcement of a specific security control. Depending on the threat model and the set of attacks under consideration, the atomic trust propositions could be combined into composite trust propositions, as demonstrated in the fourth experiment in Table 3. Consequently, a key challenge when designing a trust model can be summarized in the following hypothesis: *What is the proper level of atomicity for the target trust proposition on a trust property?*

Finally, based on the trust requirements of an organization, there are different types of SL operators (e.g., discounting, fusion, multiplication). As shown in the running example the ATL expression in Equation 3 requires the use of the Discounting and Cumulative Fusion operators, while in the evaluation of Table 3 the Multiplication operator is also used for the derivation of the composite trust proposition. Of course, there is not necessarily one operator instance that fits all cases. A good example is the fusion operator, which has different variations (e.g., Cumulative, Averaging), each of which can be applied in the appropriate context based on factors such as the independence or contradiction of the trustworthiness evidence. In fact, even within the same target trust proposition, aggregations of trust relationships may require different flavours of fusion operators. *Consequently, what are the suitable SL operators that should be chosen to accurately depict the expression for the ATL trust opinion?*

C2 - Quantifying Uncertainty in ATL: Another core challenge in the systematic modelling of the ATL methodology, is how to best manifest the quantification of uncertainty in the subjective trust modelling. As previously demonstrated, this constitutes the second core pillar dictating ATL accuracy. Uncertainty in this context primarily arises from two sources: the atomic trust opinions and expressions used to derive the ATL. In this context, uncertainty interpretation hinges on multiple factors, including the relevance of trust sources, the suitability of the selected method, and the nature of the input data used by these methods. We can categorize the sources of uncertainty into three main types:

1. Uncertainty due to limited evidence: This type of uncertainty reflects the fact that we have insufficient or incomplete information. It is typically expressed in equations by incorporating prior weight information (W in Equation 1).
2. Uncertainty in the quantification process: This arises from the inherent limitations or imprecision in the process used to quantify atomic trust opinions. This uncertainty can be caused by the methods or algorithms used in the evaluation process.
3. Uncertainty associated to each piece of evidence: In the case of atomic trust opinions, evidence is generally binary — either positive or negative. How-

ever, in practice, the confidence in each piece of evidence can vary. A more confident piece of evidence might have a greater influence on the trust level than one with lower confidence. Addressing this variability allows to maintain the binary nature of evidence while accounting for differing levels of certainty.

While these three sources of uncertainty have been identified, challenges remain in their precise quantification: (i) **Prior Weight:** The non-informative prior weight (W) can be assigned heuristically. However, determining an exact quantification for (W) remains an open challenge. *Which parameters should be considered, and how do they influence (W)?*; (ii) **Uncertainty in Quantification:** Different methods (e.g., Bayesian, fuzzy logic) and various trust sources can be used to evaluate the atomic trust opinion. Since uncertainties arise from multiple factors, *how can it be systematically quantified?* This remains an open question; (iii) **Uncertainty in Evidence Confidence:** While trust evidence is binary, confidence in each piece of evidence varies. Quantifying this confidence as uncertainty is non-trivial and remains an unresolved issue.

Beyond these challenges, further determining the appropriate type of uncertainty to model significantly increases the complexity of the problem. *Which features of the scenario should be taken into account, and how can one determine the most suitable type of uncertainty to model?* This core challenge can be generalized in how can we systematically quantify and model the different sources of uncertainty in ATL while considering either (or at the same time) the influence of prior weight, the variability in trust quantification methods, and the confidence levels of individual trust evidence.

C3 - Comparison of RTL and ATL: Moving from the ATL Methodology towards a complete trust assessment framework, it is important to express the trust requirements in a way that allows comparison of a computed ATL opinion with defined RTL constraints. From the running example, it is clear that the same pieces of evidence have different impact in organizations with different trust requirements, namely different RTL belief threshold and uncertainty modelling. In principle, the derivation of a trust decision is intrinsically linked to the accepted risk that the trustor is willing to take, with respect to the fact that a trustee behaves as expected in a given context. As part of a holistic risk assessment framework, the implementation of all security controls aims to reduce the overall risk to an accepted level. This could be the common denominator for deriving on one hand the RTL (e.g., maximum level of risk that can be considered as accepted) and on the other hand the ATL value based on evidence indicating the enforcement of the specified security controls and/or the residual risk remaining at accepted levels. Therefore, to establish a framework for assessing trust, the following question needs to be addressed: *How can both ATL value and RTL constraints be expressed in a way that reflects common knowledge, enabling comparison and the derivation of trust decisions?*

This is particularly relevant from a *decision perspective* where a trust-aware decision making is based on the trustor's own verification policies of certain metrics and/or attributes that the potential trustee presents. As mentioned above,

such evidence is essentially verifiable claims, self-issued by the trustee system, that can inform about its *reliable system operating* “as expected”, according to design and policy, doing what is required despite disruptions, errors, and attacks. However, manifesting the trust decision (through the trust opinions) on security policy conformance, comprising an optimal set of security controls and mechanisms that can minimize the impact of identified critical threats, hinges on the completeness of the evidence (as is the case with the majority of existing trust assessment methodologies - cf. Section 1.2): Whether one views them as mere, standalone tools sufficient to determine the correct (or not) enforcement of a security control; e.g., positive or negative evidence on SW stack configuration integrity has a direct impact on system security.

However, these do not follow an either-or model, which is why a more nuanced view of the dependencies between composable security mechanisms is needed. For instance, the verification and validation of runtime operational safeguards, such as Control-Flow Integrity and/or Control-Flow Attestation [2], while can provide strong integrity guarantees, they can negate (or significantly impact) system dependability by violating safety and availability requirements as they introduce additional attack vectors (e.g., exploitation of the dynamically defined control transfers occurring during the tracing of an operation of interest leading to control-flow violations). Thus, the question arises *how these dependencies can be captured and transferred into the subjective logic model in order to correctly calculate the ATL?* Direct and transitive security dependencies can be modelled as (dis-)beliefs on the impact of each security control, and its associated evidence, in the overall trust expression or as opinions affecting the confidence level of employed positive security controls. Whatever approach is adopted, this needs to be mirrored in both ATL and RTL definitions so as to enable their verification, validation and evaluation.

C4 - Evolution of Trust: The dynamic nature of scenarios calls for dynamic trust evaluation, where new evidence continually shapes the assessment of trust levels. The fundamental question is how new evidence should be incorporated into the evaluation process. We differentiate between two approaches.

1. **Recalculate the ATL (1):** This approach suggests reassessing the updating some evidence using new one. A potential concern with this approach is that dropping the previous evaluation entirely could lead to a loss of historical information, which may be critical for understanding long-term trust patterns.
2. **Revise the ATL (2):** Alternatively, we can revise the previous trust level (ω_{t-1}) by incorporating the new evidence into the existing trust framework. This approach aims to preserve prior information while integrating fresh data, thus maintaining continuity in trust assessments. The revision process can be modelled using a weighted average formula, such as:

$$\omega_t = \alpha\omega_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha)\omega_{\text{new}} \quad (4)$$

where ω_t is the updated trust level, ω_{t-1} is the previous trust level, ω_{new} is the trust level derived from new evidence, and $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a weight parameter that controls the influence of past versus new evidence.

However, this approach raises also some challenges:

- **Conflict and Dependency Between Opinions:** There might be conflicting or dependent relationships between the previous trust opinion (ω_{t-1}) and the new trust evaluation (ω_{new}), complicating the revision process. A simple weighted average like the one in Equation 4 may not be sufficient to resolve these conflicts. Thus, using an appropriate fusion operator might help to overcome this challenge.
- **Determining the Value of α :** The value of α is not trivial to determine. It could either be static or dynamic, depending on factors such as the reliability of the new evidence or the volume of data. A dynamic α would adapt over time, allowing for a more flexible revision process that considers the evolving quality of evidence.

Overall, the core challenge is *how can we systematically model the evolution of trust while balancing historical information, integrating new evidence, and determining the appropriate fusion operator or dynamic adaptation of trust parameters such as α ?*

C5 - Convolution of Trust: Federated TAF refers to the collaboration between different TAFs to enhance reliability and improve performance. This collaboration can occur at various stages of the TAF process. One key stage is the creation of the trust model. Since an individual TAF may have an incomplete or limited perspective, collaborating with other TAFs enables a more comprehensive and accurate trust model. Another crucial aspect is evidence or opinion sharing. After constructing the trust model, TAFs can exchange trust-related evidence, observations, or subjective opinions to refine their assessments.

In most multi-agent systems, the trustor and the trustee are distinct agents. Now, consider a scenario where two TAFs operate within Agent 1 and Agent 2 respectively. It is important to note that not every node in a Trust Model necessarily hosts a TAF, as resource constraints may limit their deployment. However, the described scenario can also be extended to cases where local TAFs operate within subnetworks, assessing trust at a more granular level. In our scenario of Agent 1 and Agent 2, the challenge is that the evidence required for Agent 2’s evaluation is generated on Agent 1 itself (e.g., attestation evidence about the sensor), meaning the TAF in Agent 2 does not have direct access to that evidence. The question then is how to handle and exchange trust evidence between federated TAFs.

The most straightforward approach is to transmit the raw trust evidence from Agent 1 to Agent 2. However, this evidence often contains sensitive information, making direct sharing a risk of data leaks or unauthorized access. In addition, the transmission of evidence between agents leads to high communication overhead, increasing bandwidth usage, which may not be available. A better approach is to enable TAFs to exchange trust opinions instead of raw evidence.

In that case, a key challenge is to ensure trust consistency and interpretability across federated entities. Since each TAF generates its own trust opinion based on locally available evidence and specific trust models, differences in opinion computation, trust model, or contextual assumptions can lead to inconsistencies in trust assessments. Beyond simply sharing trust opinions, a TAF can also share the underlying trust expression used in its evaluation. This not only facilitates better interoperability but also enhances the explainability of trust assessments, allowing other TAFs to understand the logic behind the computed trust values.

Despite these potential solutions, challenges remain in ensuring reliable and efficient trust convolution across federated entities. *How can federated TAFs effectively exchange, interpret, and integrate trust evidence or opinions while maintaining consistency, security, and minimal communication overhead?*

6 Conclusion

In this work, we proposed a universally applicable trust assessment methodology that can be adapted and applied in the context of any application domain, including in multi-agent, distributed environments, taking into consideration different trust requirements and propositions. The first step of this process entails the generation of expressions for the calculation of the ATL of atomic and composite trust propositions, the operators employed, and the trust model creation. The second step pertains to the collection of the required trustworthiness evidence and the formation of trust opinions. The final step involves the evaluation of trust expressions by integrating the derived trust opinions for the computation of trustworthiness. The applicability of this methodology was demonstrated in practice in a smart ambulance scenario, and a set of challenges were laid out in order to facilitate the adaptation of the proposed scheme to the specific needs of any desired use case. Future work includes the demonstration of the proposed methodology in various other practical domains and application scenarios.

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